

Incentive-Plus, a Driver of Knowledge and Hospital Delivery Uptake among Pregnant Women in Rural Communities in Benue State

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, less than half of pregnant women have adequate knowledge of hospital delivery, and most home deliveries occur among women who do not attend ANC, particularly in rural areas. This is largely driven by low socioeconomic status and poor education. This study assessed the effectiveness of sustained health education and mama kit incentives in improving knowledge and uptake of facility-based delivery. A quasi-experimental study was conducted across twelve communities. Sampling technique was multistage, with statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

The overall baseline knowledge of health facility delivery was good in both the study (77.9%) and control (80.5%) groups. In the study group, a monthly income $\geq \text{₦}10,000$ and formal education were significant predictors of good knowledge of hospital delivery (OR = 2.21; 95% CI: 0.93–5.24) and (OR = 2.97; 95% CI: 1.38–6.38), respectively. Similarly, a monthly income $\geq \text{₦}10,000$ was a significant predictor of hospital delivery in both the study (OR = 2.29; 95% CI: 1.26–5.58) and control (OR = 2.83; 95% CI: 1.32–6.08) groups. Following the intervention, there was a statistically significant increase in both knowledge and hospital delivery uptake in the study group. In conclusion, the intervention improved knowledge and uptake of hospital delivery. A coordinated state–federal partnership is recommended to scale up awareness campaigns and provide Mama Kits to pregnant women, thereby enhancing the utilization of facility-based delivery services.

Keywords: health facility delivery, Incentives, knowledge, promote, rural communities

INTRODUCTION

Maternal health outcomes, particularly maternal mortality remain a critical public health concern in many low-resource settings, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where preventable complications during pregnancy and childbirth continue to contribute significantly to maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality.¹ Nigeria, in particular, accounts for nearly

20% of global maternal deaths, with a maternal mortality ratio (MMR) estimated at over 512 deaths per 100,000 live births with a 40% reduction between 2000 to 2023.^{2,3} Despite global efforts to promote skilled birth attendance, many pregnant women in rural communities still rely on traditional birth attendants or deliver at home without skilled supervision.^{4,5} In Nigeria, and specifically in Benue State, limited access to healthcare services, cultural beliefs, financial constraints, and

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inadequate knowledge about the benefits of skilled delivery have been identified as prominent barriers to optimal maternal health-seeking behaviour.^{3,6,7} These factors underscore the need for context-specific interventions that not only improve access to maternal health services but also enhance pregnant women's knowledge and motivation to utilize health facilities for childbirth.⁶

Prepackaged delivery kits containing essential items required for hygienic childbirth have emerged as an innovative and practical incentive to encourage facility-based deliveries.⁸ These kits typically include items such as gloves, plastic sheets, disinfectants, cord clamps, and sanitary materials, which help ensure a clean and safe delivery.^{9,10} By reducing the cost burden associated with procuring delivery supplies, mama kits serve as an enabling factor for pregnant women who may otherwise perceive facility delivery as financially demanding.¹¹ In Nigeria, more than half (56%) of live births are delivered at home in the absence of a skilled birth attendant, while only 43% are delivered in a health facility. Health facility births have increased slightly since 1990, from 32% to 43%.³ Home births are more common among women with no education and in the poorest households (both 82%).¹³ In rural communities where economic limitations are common, the provision of mama kits can serve as a strong motivator for expectant mothers to choose skilled delivery services over home births.¹²

In addition to material incentives, health education remains a cornerstone of effective maternal health interventions.¹³ Health education empowers pregnant women with knowledge about the dangers of home delivery, the importance of antenatal care, birth preparedness, and the benefits of skilled attendance during childbirth.¹⁴ For women in rural Benue State, culturally appropriate and accessible health education programs delivered through antenatal clinics, community outreach, or trained community volunteers can significantly enhance understanding and positively influence health-seeking decisions.¹⁵ Improved knowledge is strongly associated with increased uptake of recommended maternal health services, including

hospital deliveries.^{16,17} While mama kits provide tangible support that alleviates financial constraints, health education builds capacity for informed decision-making. Together, they create an enabling environment that supports pregnant women to choose safe delivery options.¹⁷ Understanding the effectiveness of this integrated strategy to improve health facility delivery is crucial for informing policy, strengthening maternal health programs, and guiding state-level implementation of cost-effective interventions.¹⁸

Despite growing recognition of the potential of these interventions, there is limited empirical evidence on how the combined effect of mama kits and health education influences hospital delivery uptake and knowledge levels among pregnant women in rural Benue State.

This study, therefore, aims to assess the extent to which mama kits, alongside targeted health education, drive the uptake of hospital deliveries and improve maternal health knowledge among pregnant women in rural communities of Benue State. The findings aim to contribute to evidence-based strategies that enhance safe motherhood and reduce preventable maternal and neonatal outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted in twelve (12) rural communities in Benue State. The population of Benue State was projected to reach 6,888,980 in 2023, with an annual growth rate of 3%.¹⁹ The state has a total of 1,408 health facilities, including 862 publicly owned primary health facilities, 427 privately owned primary health facilities, 24 public secondary facilities, 93 private secondary facilities, and 3 government-owned tertiary health facilities. The major ethnic groups in Benue State are Tiv, Idoma, and Igede, while English is the official language. The 20 most predominant rural Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the state were grouped into three senatorial zones: A, B, and C, from which the study areas were selected. Zone A comprises Konshisha, Kwande, Logo, Ukum, Ushongo, and Vandeikya. Zone B includes Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer East, Gwer

West, Makurdi, and Tarka. Zone C consists of Ado, Agatu, Apa, Obi, Ogbadibo, Ohimini, Okpokwu, Oju, and Otukpo.

Study design

A quasi-experimental study was conducted among pregnant women residing in twenty rural communities in Benue State.

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size for this study was 380, determined using the formula for comparing two proportions in two independent study groups, while accounting for both Type I (alpha) and Type II (beta) errors.

$$n = \frac{(z_{\alpha} + z_{\beta})^2 \times 2 \times p(1-p)}{(P_1 - P_2)^2}$$

Where n = minimum sample size

Z_{α} = z value for α -error at 1.96 confidence level and 95% confidence interval

z_{β} = z value for β -error at 80% power on the normal distribution corresponding to 100%- power.

After adjusting for non-response rate (f) of 10%

$n' = n/1-f$, A sample size of 190 was obtained for the study group and 190 for the control group.

Sampling technique

Stage one: (Selection of L.G.As)

Out of the twenty (20) predominantly rural Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Benue State, six (6) LGAs were selected for the control group and six (6) LGAs for the study group using a simple random sampling technique (balloting).

Stage two: (Selection of communities)

Communities with catchment primary health care centres (PHCs) in the selected study and control LGAs were listed. Six (6) communities were selected from the study LGAs and six (6) communities were selected from the control LGAs using simple random sampling (balloting).

Stage three: (Selection of actual respondents)

Each of the selected community in the study group was mapped and numbered. Households in the communities were counted, and recorded. Pregnant women in each household were counted and listed in the household register. Probability proportionate sampling was used to determine the number of participants to be studied in each selected community using the formula below.

$$\text{Number of eligible participants} = \frac{\text{Total Number of pregnant women in each community}}{\text{Total Number of pregnant women in the 6 communities}} \times 190$$

Systematic sampling was used to select the actual participants for the study. This procedure was repeated in the control group to select the participants and a total sample size of 380 was obtained for both groups.

Inclusion criteria

Consenting pregnant women of reproductive age whose gestational age was ≤ 26 weeks and were residing in selected twelve (12) rural communities of Benue State were enrolled in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Pregnant women who were temporary visitors and those who had already received structured birth preparedness education from previous programs or facility less than one year before commencement of the study were excluded.

Instrument of data collection

Data was collected using a semi-structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire with both closed- and open-ended questions, adapted from the validated 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) tool. The questionnaire was translated into Tiv, Idoma, and Igede languages to ensure cultural appropriateness. It captured socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge of health facility delivery, and associated factors. A pretest was conducted among 30 pregnant women in Tarhembe community, Tarka LGA, to ensure clarity, timing, and reliability of the instrument. The intervention for the study group consisted of six birth preparedness-focused health education sessions, which highlighted the importance of consistent antenatal care

attendance, the benefits of facility-based delivery, and maternal and neonatal health advantages, followed by the distribution of a well-packaged incentive delivery kit (Mama kit). Follow-up data was collected from both groups after delivery at baseline (pre-intervention) and post-intervention stages.

Data Management

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 20. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. Chi-square test, Fisher's exact test, and logistic regression were used to compare proportions. The pretested instrument assessed socio-demographic characteristics, obstetric history, and knowledge and utilization of hospital delivery services, ensuring validity, appropriateness, and researcher familiarity with the tool.

Indices of assessment, scoring and grading

Outcome variables were Knowledge scores (level) of hospital deliveries, uptake of hospital deliveries and their predictors. Baseline data was collected to determine the knowledge and utilization of hospital deliveries. Six sessions of sustained health talks were carried and Mama Kits were administered to participants among the study group. However, after baseline data collection there was none of such intervention among the control group. Participants were assessed based on six (6) components of health facility delivery. In the knowledge domain, each correct response was awarded one (1) mark while a wrong or don't know was awarded zero (0) mark²⁰. Scores of 50% and above were classified as good, while those below 50% were considered poor using the modified blooms criteria²⁰

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was sought from the ethical committee of Benue State Ministry of Health before the commencement of the study. Permission was obtained from the Primary Health Care Development Board and the local government chairmen of the selected LGAs. An advocacy visit was paid to village heads of selected communities to inform them about the study and solicit their support. Informed written consent was also obtained from the participants before the study.

RESULTS

All (380) respondents were interviewed in the study and control groups giving a response rate of 100% at baseline. However, 177 responded in the study group after intervention with an attrition rate of 7% while 181 responded in the control group after follow-up with an attrition rate of 5%. The study and control groups had mean ages of 24.09 ± 5.48 and 25.77 ± 5.92 years, predominantly aged 15–24. Nearly all respondents were married, mostly Tiv, and overwhelmingly Christian. Secondary education was most common (57.9% and 44.2%), followed by primary (31.1% and 20.0%) and tertiary levels (5.8% and 10%), in both study and control groups with slightly higher secondary and primary education rates in the study group compared to the control group (Table 1). In both groups, most respondents were farmers (82.6% control; 76.8% study), followed by business and civil service. Majority earned less than ₦30,000 monthly. Parity was mostly 1–4 children in control (70.5%) and 1–3 in study (58.9%). Husbands' occupations mirrored respondents', with most being farmers, followed by business and civil service across both groups. (Table 2).

In the study group, majority of respondents (77.1%) had good knowledge of hospital delivery at baseline, after the intervention, almost all the respondents (95.5%) had good knowledge of hospital delivery. The difference was statistically significant ($p=0.001$). However, in the control group majority of respondents (80.5%) had good knowledge of hospital delivery at baseline, after the intervention, the proportion of respondents with good knowledge decreased to (78.5%). This could possibly be due to lack sustained health education in the control group may lead to inconsistent ANC attendance which could further weaken baseline knowledge. The difference was not statistically significant $p=0.700$ (Table 3).

Formal education was the only statistically significant predictor of the knowledge of health facility deliveries, only in the control group. Respondents who were educated were 3 times more likely to have good knowledge of health facilities compared with respondents who did not have formal education

(p=0.005) (Table 5). In the study group, less than half of the respondents (45.8%) delivered in a health facility at baseline. However, in the control group, slightly less than half of the respondents (48.9) had a health facility delivery at baseline. The difference was not statistically significant, p=0.709 (Figure 1). In the study group, nearly half of the respondents (45.8%) had health facility delivery at baseline; after the intervention, the majority of the respondents (77.4%) had health facility delivery. The difference was statistically significant (p=0.001). Similarly, in the control group, almost half of the respondents (48.9%) had health facility delivery at the beginning of the study, and at the end of the study, only (45.3%) of the respondents had health facility delivery. The difference was statistically significant,

p=0.009 (Table 6).

Income was a statistically significant predictor of health facility delivery in both the study and control groups. Participants whose income was higher than ₦30,000 were 2.3 times more likely to have a hospital delivery (p<0.05). Similarly in the control group, respondents whose income was higher than ₦30,000 were 2.8 times more likely to have a hospital delivery compared with those earning less than ₦30,000 monthly. However, formal education was a statistically significant predictor of hospital delivery in the control group. Respondents who had formal education in the control group were 2.2 times more likely to have a hospital delivery compared with those who had no formal education, p=0.001 (Table 7).

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Study Group N=190	Control group N=190	Chi-Square test	p-value
Age group (years)			2.822	0.60
15 – 24	112(58.9)	91(47.9)		
25 – 34	65(34.2)	82(43.2)		
35 – 44	13(6.8)	17(8.9)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Mean(±SD)	24.09±5.48	25.77±5.92		
Marital Status			1.218*	0.596
Married	190(100)	188(98.9)		
Single/Widowed	0(0.0)	2(1.1)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Ethnicity			5.656*	0.463
Tiv	122(64.2)	118(62.1)		
Idoma	29(15.3)	35(18.4)		
Igede	37(19.5)	35(18.4)		
Others	2(1.1)	2(1.1)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Religion			0.96*	1.00
Christian	188(98.9)	190(100)		
Muslim	2(1.1)	0(0.0)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Educational Status			13.594	0.138
No Education	10(5.3)	49(25.8)		
Primary	59(31.1)	38(20)		
Secondary	110(57.9)	84(44.2)		
Tertiary	11(5.8)	19(10.0)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		

**Others: Ethnic groups include: Igbo and Hausa

* Fisher's exact test

Table 2: Distribution of Occupation, Monthly income, Husband's occupation and Parity of Respondents

VARIABLE	Study Group N=100	Control Group N=100	ChiSquare test	p-value
Occupation			6.049	0.304
Farming	146(76.8)	157(82.6)		
Business	32(16.8)	23(12.1)		
Civil servant	6(3.2)	8(4.2)		
Others	6(3.2)	2(1.1)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Monthly Income (₦)			0.343	0.643
< ₦30,000	117(61.6)	120(63.2)		
≥ ₦30,000	73 (38.4)	70(36.8)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Parity			0.003	1.0
Primigravida	40(21.1)	36(18.9)		
1-4	112(58.9)	134(70.5)		
≥ 5	38(20.0)	20(10.5)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		
Husbands Occupation			12.371	0.185
Business	30(15.8)	23(12.1)		
Civil Servant	20(10.5)	19(10.0)		
Farming	115(60.5)	143(75.3)		
Others	25(13.2)	5(2.6)		
Total	190(100)	190(100)		

*Fisher's exact test

Table 3: Pre- and Post-Intervention Knowledge Score of Respondents of Hospital Delivery by study status

Variable	Study group		Control group	
	Before intervention n=(190) Frequency (%)	After intervention n=(177) Frequency (%)	Beginning of study n=(190) Frequency (%)	End of study n=(181) Frequency (%)
Good Knowledge	148(77.1)	169 (95.5)	153(80.5)	142(78.5)
Poor Knowledge	42(22.9)	8(4.5)	37(19.5)	39(21.5)
Total	190(100)	177(100)	190(100)	181(100)
	Chi-Square = 24.081, p=0.001		Chi-Square =0.245, p =0.700	

Figure 1: A Simple Bar-Chart Showing the Participants Uptake of Hospital Delivery by Study Status

Chi Square test = 2.177, p = 0.709

Table 4: Factors associated with baseline knowledge of Health facility deliveries

Variable	Study Group n=190 Frequency (%)		Control Group n=190 Frequency (%)	
	Good Knowledge	Poor Knowledge	Good Knowledge	Poor Knowledge
Age				
< 25	85(44.7)	27(14.2)	72(37.9)	18(20)
≥ 25	63(33.2)	15(7.9)	81(42.6)	19(19)
Total	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	153(80.5)	37(19.5)
	Chi-Square = 0.635, p = 0.480		Chi-Square = 0.030, p = 1.000	
Marital status				
Married	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	Married	148(77.9)
Single/Widowed	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	Single/Widowed	0(0.0)
Total	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	Total	148(77.9)
	Fisher's exact test = -, p = -		Fisher's exact test= 0.489, p = 1.000	
Ethnicity				
Indigene	147(77.4)	41(21.6)	151(79.5)	37(19.5)
Non-Indigene	1(0.5)	1(0.5)	2(1.1)	0(0.0)
Total	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	153(80.5)	37(19.5)
	Fisher's exact test = 0.913, p = 0.394		Fisher's exact test= 0.489, p = 1.000	
StatuSSstatus				
No Formal Education	8(4.2)	2(1.1)	32(16.8)	17(8.9)
Formal Education	140(73.7)	40(21.1)	121(63.7)	20(10.5)
Total	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	153(80.5)	37(19.5)
	Fisher's exact test = 0.027, p = 1.000		Chi-Square = 9.754, p = 0.003	
Occupation				
Farming	110(57.9)	36(18.9)	125(65.8)	32(16.8)
Business	27(14.2)	5(2.6)	18(9.5)	5(2.6)
Civil servant	6(3.2)	0(0.0)	8(4.2)	0(0.0)
Others	5(2.6%)	1(0.5)	2(1.1)	0(0.0)
Total	148(77.9)	42(22.1)	153(80.5)	37(19.5)
	Fisher's exact test= 2.418, p = 0.486		Fisher's exact test= 1.895, p = 0.668	

Table 5: Binary Logistic regression of factors affecting knowledge of health facility deliveries

Variables	Study Group			Control Group		
	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value
Educational status						
No formal education	1			1		
Formal education	0.833	0.169 – 4.116	0.823	2.971	1.383 – 6.383	0.005
Income						
<₦30,000	1			1		
≥₦30,000	1.759	0.834 – 3.708	0.138	2.211	0.932 – 5.243	0.072
Age						
<25	1			1		
≥25	1.33	0.661 – 2.723	0.430	1.066	0.520 – 2.184	0.861

Table 6: Pre-and Post-Intervention Uptake of Hospital Deliveries among Respondents by Study Status

Variables	Study group		Control group	
	Before intervention n=(150) Frequency (%)	After intervention n=(177) Frequency (%)	Beginning of study n=(154) Frequency (%)	End of study n=(181) Frequency (%)
Health Facility Delivery	88(45.8)	137(77.4)	92(48.9%)	82(45.3)
Home Delivery	62(32.1)	40(22.6)	62(33.2%)	99(54.7)
	150(100)	177(100)	154(81.05%)	181(100)
	Chi-Square = 13.27 p=0.001		Chi-Square = 6.947 p=0.009	

Primigravida were excluded at baseline since they had no previous experience of place of delivery

Table 7: Binary Logistic regression for significant factors affecting Health Facility Delivery

Variable	Study Group			Control Group		
	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval	p-value
Educational status						
Formal Education	2.034	0.509 – 8.123	0.315	4.787	2.161 – 10.602	0.001
No formal Education	1			1		
Income						
< ₦30,000	1			1		
≥ ₦30,000	2.287	1.133 – 4.613	0.021	2.833	1.320 – 6.079	0.008

DISCUSSION

Findings from this study showed that most of the respondents had good knowledge of health facility deliveries in both study and control groups at baseline. There was also a statistically significant increase in knowledge in the study group. This finding was different from findings in Bangladesh, Tanzania, Ethiopia, and Sokoto, in which the majority of the women had poor knowledge of Health facility delivery, emergency preparedness, and complication readiness.

The finding could be a result of the high proportion of primigravida in the study in Ethiopia, a high proportion of respondents with primary education in the study in Tanzania, and a very high proportion of women with no formal education in Sokoto, Nigeria. A pregnant woman who has good knowledge of health facility delivery has a higher tendency of utilizing the services of a skilled birth attendant at delivery with good maternal and foetal outcomes^{21,22,23,24}. An intervention study in Sokoto State and Zambia showed a similar result in which health education improves the knowledge of health facility

delivery as well as its utilization.^{25,26}

A significant predictor of health facility deliveries was formal education in the control group. In this study, respondents who had formal education were 2.9 times more likely to have good knowledge of health facility delivery. This finding is similar to findings in Tanzania, Ethiopia, and Sokoto, Nigeria, where women's educational status was associated with the knowledge of health facility deliveries.^{24,27} In this study, respondents who had health facility delivery were slightly less than half in both the study and control groups. This finding is similar to findings in community-based studies in Ethiopia, Ghana, Nigeria, and the NDHS 2018, where the utilization of health facilities for delivery was less than half. Studies in Afghanistan and Katsina, Nigeria, show a very contrasting finding with very low health facility utilization for delivery of 13.0%. The finding of very low utilization in the studies could be due to a very high level of illiteracy of 94% and 63%^{28,27,29,30}. When a woman utilizes a health facility, she comes in contact with a skilled birth attendant who prepares her for safe delivery. She learns about complications of pregnancy and delivery, such as postpartum haemorrhage, obstructed labor, high blood pressure in pregnancy and ways of averting them. She knows the importance of health facility delivery and makes her plans towards delivery in a health facility to avert these eventualities.

To assess the effect of the intervention in the utilization of health facility for delivery, there was a statistically significant increase in the utilization of health facilities for delivery from 45.8% before intervention to 77.4% after intervention in the study group and a reduction of 48.9 utilization to 45.3% after follow-up in the control group. This finding is also in line with the qualitative findings where respondents agree to utilize health facility if given incentive. This finding was in contrast to a finding in Kwara, Nigeria where health education intervention did not increase the utilization of health facilities for delivery. There was, however, an increase in knowledge of health facility delivery. This finding agreed with a study in Lagos, Nigeria where there was an increase in the utilization of health facilities for delivery from baseline after health education

intervention. A study in India also shows that there was an increase in health facility delivery to 85.0% in the study group compared to the control group of 78.5% after follow-up^{31,32,33}. The finding in this study showed very high effectiveness compared to other studies because this study was a combination of two intervention which could have a synergistic effect on the outcome.

Also, the knowledge of health facility delivery increased by 18.4% after intervention. This finding is in consonance with two studies in Sokoto, Nigeria, Nigeria where respondents had a statistically significant increase in knowledge of health facility delivery after intervention. The finding in this study showed that the intervention was effective^{34,35}

Exploring the predictors of health facility utilization showed that the predictors were formal education and income. Education and income of women increased the likelihood of health facility delivery in this study at baseline. This finding is in line with the qualitative where most of the respondents seek the services of an SBA and quality care when utilizing a health facility for delivery. Educated women know the importance of a skilled birth attendant.

A community-based study in Senegal, and two facility-based studies in Uyo, and Anambra, Nigeria show similar findings where women who were well educated and with high income and wealth quintile had a higher likelihood of health facility delivery. A study carried out in Kano, Nigeria, showed a different finding with women with a high number of ANC contacts and who had planned delivery location had about two to nine times more likelihood to deliver in a health facility compared with those who had not planned for a place of delivery and had low ANC utilisation^{36,37,38}. Health facility delivery is an indirect estimate of the utilization of skilled birth attendants. Women who are well educated and have good incomes, as found in this study, have increased access to skilled birth assistance at birth. Access to skilled delivery would lead to better management of anticipated complications and reduced maternal morbidity and mortality.

CONCLUSION

The study found that women demonstrated good baseline knowledge of health facility deliveries. Having a formal education was a significant predictor of good knowledge of health facility delivery. Also, there was a statistically significant increase in the utilization of health facilities for delivery after the intervention only in the study group, and formal education was a significant predictor of health facility delivery.

Recommendations

Improving community education is essential, as it predicts knowledge and utilization. Periodic health talks and awareness campaigns on antenatal care and facility delivery, targeting women, should be implemented through government and non-governmental organizations. The state government, through the state primary health care board, should include the Mama Kit/health talk program in their annual budget of the Basic Health Care Provision Fund to improve utilization of hospitals for ANC and deliveries

Limitations

Since the study was conducted in selected rural communities, the findings may vary from urban settings or other regions with different socio-cultural, economic, and health system characteristics. Variations in health infrastructure, educational levels, and accessibility to health facilities may limit the broader applicability of the results.

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Conflict of Interests

we declare that we have no competing interest as a reviewer.

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